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Abstract

The report provides success stories, guidance and lessons learnt during the deployment of procuRE.

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Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

1 Project mission and success stories

Our project attempted to utilise procurement of innovation to research and develop new methods and tools to de-fossilise the building stock. The focus was put on buildings with moderate efficiency, i.e. buildings which would under normal circumstances not be approached with envelope measures but constitute a large proportion of existing buildings using fossil energy and thus directly responsible for large quantities of greenhouse gas emissions we attempted to remove (i.e. de-fossilise).

In our mission, we identified a range of challenges and requested the market to develop three innovations covering i) renovation planning and design process, ii) de-fossilisation renovations of existing building and iii) developing and demonstrating advancements in an existing product category (BMS / BACS). Whilst the de-fossilisation approach has proven itself (ii) and the system integration (iii) has been proven possible even in older buildings, more work is needed to develop more time-efficient and reliable design and planning procedures.

For readers interested in innovation procurement, we openly advice not to attempt three conceptually different innovations – no matter how complementary – within one lot. However, it is also the nature of R&D efforts that not all attempts can be successful as it would otherwise would not have been ambitious. Furthermore, even in struggle there are lessons as well as insights for new ideas.

Our approach to sharing insight

This report is written in a transparent manner. We describe our successes as well as challenges, exogenous or self-induced, their causes as well as how to fully avoid or mitigate these challenges.

We wish to be instructive and share what we learned. We believe future procurers of de-fossilisation of buildings renovations and innovation procurement (i.e. pre-commercial procurements, PCPs) can benefit from this report as our project was a “first” in various regards:

- procuRE is the first PCP to procure tangible renovations in existing buildings as part of an innovation procurement;
- procuRE is the first PCP to navigate the complexities of EU VAT-law in context of cross-border joint procurement of tangible assets we had to navigate with conflicting expert opinion;
- We developed and monitored indicators suitable to plan and assess de-fossilisation renovations;
- We demonstrate the environmental potential of low-investment de-fossilisation renovations focusing on active systems generating data and insights outside of the mainstream.
- We demonstrate that a large improvement of the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) is possible in existing buildings using only moderate investments.

We are confident our mission and the underlying needs remain valid. We are convinced that – on socio-economic level - the de-fossilisation approach is an effective way to reduce GHG emissions in buildings accommodating the general push to higher envelope efficiency.

This deliverable focuses on lessons and the future. The demonstrations sites in context of which the lesson were learnt are described in the parallel deliverable D7.5.

1.1 Mission: faster means to de-fossilise existing buildings

The legislative overhaul of Fit for 55 profoundly increases the ambition and urgency of achieving climate targets. Buildings account for >40% of all energy consumed. The recast of the EPBD focuses on stricter targets for decarbonising and reducing fossil dependency in both the existing and newly constructed building stock. Renovation of the existing buildings remains the biggest challenge due to the complexity, diversity and implementation barriers. By 2050 all existing buildings should be transformed into zero-emission buildings. The EED requires all cities above 45,000 inhabitants to develop heating and cooling plans. 75% of the existing building stock is inefficient and requires action to reach zero-emission targets by 2050.

The shared ambition of the procuRE consortium

The cities in the innovation procurement procuRE have ambitious net-zero targets. To succeed energy consumption in all public buildings must be tackled within the next 10-15 years. This is impossible, given the workload of regular renovation projects as well as various constraints described in further detail below. Instead, the project aims to identify approaches which merge efficiency first for high-energy systems (e.g. HVAC, light), on-site renewable energy sources and storage whilst integrating old systems to ensure efficient operation. The original Challenge Brief describes the varying challenges for large-scale pick-up in detail.¹

Achieving zero-emission target in existing building stock

The performance of the buildings stock can be displayed by sorting each building from high consumption to low consumption. The resulting graphic shows the distribution of buildings' average yearly energy consumption as a function of the building stock share. The concept is similar to a load duration curve² used for energy systems and in energy production.

Figure 1. Building stock sorted by level of consumption– exemplary depiction³

¹ <https://procure-pcp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/procuRE-RfT-TD2-Challenge-Brief-SHORT.pdf>

² See references on Springer: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/engineering/load-duration-curve>

³ Since data access to EPCs is limited and not harmonised the exact shape of the profile is unknown and content of the recommendation.

Following the efficiency first principle, the current EU policy targeting the building stock consists of two major vectors:

- The **focus is on high-consumption buildings** to reap the lowest-hanging fruit with the highest energetic return on investment (e.g. minimum requirements, incentives, renovation passports).
- **Long-term**, the consumption of the entire building stock is to be pushed downwards by a large number of measures such building standards on national level and implementation of renovation passports on individual level.

*procuRE aims to add advance another vector to complement the strategy **with a focus on de-fossilisation**. The aim is to add an additional **short-term** pillar targeting buildings with adequate envelope quality to electrify and de-fossilise consumption to the largest possible degree provided it is possible to achieve this with minimal planning and construction effort and at low costs.*

Our focus is on buildings not sufficiently high in the priority for envelope measures, due to the envelope not requiring any maintenance and/or efficiency being at average, but still significant emitters of GHG which are, in fact, the majority of buildings. The concept is also transferable to any renovation.

Figure 2. Efficiency strategies and new contribution of procuRE

Example of consumption (and emissions) in a municipal building stock

The structure of existing local buildings stocks is a key driver in the search for an alternative approach to reduce energy consumption and emissions. The below graphic depicts the building stock of a mid-sized city as data points mapped by their total consumption and specific energy consumption per square meter (actual data as of 2024).

Figure 3. Sample Building Stock of a medium-sized City – Heating Energy Consumption

The distribution of buildings thins out in both dimensions. The largest number of buildings has small or medium sized consumption with varying levels of efficiency. This corresponds well with the fact that most buildings are small and mid-sized.

Current city activity often focuses on the small number of large consumers and buildings with very low efficiency. For the rest of the building stock – smaller and medium-sized buildings – renovations are driven by need to do something bringing along some energy savings. These renovations are extremely labour intensive in planning, commissioning and implementation.

For most cities and local economies, the current “renovation load” is already overburdening – this includes both the municipal staff as well as most trades required. Availability of easily accessible funds clearly play a role as recent years have shown that increasing local demand combined with the material dependency of Europe will result in high prices eventually reducing the total number of renovations. To progress, horizontal measures such as deployment of heat pumps are sometimes undertaken. However, inappropriate installations typically omit efficiency potentials and are poorly integrated with legacy systems. Whilst combination with RES is obvious, it is often omitted or poorly designed inducing medium-term risk of congestion in the local grid.

procuRE investigated solutions which are able to tackle the large number smaller and medium sized buildings. The measures should utilise economies of scale, minimise material use, can be undertaken within a couple of months. This will enable cities to utilise precocious capacity on low efficiency building stock.

1.2 Success stories

1.2.1 De-fossilise buildings and reduce GHG at positive socio-economic return

The project tackled three schools and three office buildings. The renovation deployed active systems and integrated them to replace on-site fossils (in some cases, existing electricity-based systems e.g. heat pump systems) and the highest part possible of grid energy with on-site energy production with PV, batteries and HVAC systems monitored and controlled through BMS. The following statistics demonstrate the success of renovations that do not tackle the envelope first, and therefore call into question the assumption that envelope measures always need to come first. This has been achieved despite numerous price-hikes the project had to compensate:

- 78% of on-site fossil-based energy (oil, gas) has been replaced with electricity.
- 75% of GHG emissions caused by buildings has been avoided.
- 42% of consumption is covered by on-site RES and battery systems, with four out of six pilot sites above 50 %⁴.
- 6,060 tonnes of CO₂ equivalent will be avoided by 2050.
- Five of six buildings reduce their overall demand from the grid.
- Final energy consumption increased by 10% (i.e. electricity for heat pumps) with efficiency potentials not fully utilised due to budget constraints as result of price shocks.
- Considering avoided costs of GHG, the investment results in 2.7 Euro for each Euro invested⁵.
- Average spending for equipment per building amounted to EUR 375,000.
- Available capacity, in terms of both energy and power, for flexibility of up to 540kW rated power (56% battery, 44% HVAC) with 550kWh battery capacity.
- Black start capability demonstrated at one site.
- Cooling ability improved in two sites improving occupant comfort.

The renovations have been conducted in **representative buildings of moderate envelope quality**. These are buildings where envelope measures are not anticipated to be necessary for 20-30 years. The implementation has been achieved during several months and during regular operation of the building with work typically carried out during holiday seasons, evenings or weekends avoiding downtime and the related costs of organisation, logistics and inconvenience for the occupants. The building types are schools and small and mid-sized offices with immense replication potential.

Technologies used are available at scale and produced in industrial settings with great potential for further price decreases. All devices can be ordered within months of planning, short-term shocks aside, reducing risks to budgets. Planning and renovations can be planned, tendered and organised in framework contracts enabling advantages of economies of scale. This approach is suitable for the emerging infrastructure packages at EU level and Member States (e.g. Germany).

Our success of deploying the ‘active renovation’ can be repeated by almost any municipality (or portfolio manager), especially if our lessons are considered regarding organising the tender and the implementation.

⁴ This figure covers the timely overlap of RES production and battery storage. The share would have been higher if the originally foreseen battery capacity would have been procured. As battery is a flexible item, it was first victim to the effects of supply crisis, price increases and inflation.

⁵ Figure includes the recuperation of investment costs (i.e. the investment pays for itself and adds another 1.7 Euro per Euro invested). Taking the numbers for the four EU sites, the figure remains positive with 1.92 per Euro invested.

Fast-paced de-fossilisation using the integration of active systems is a viable approach at scale and can lead to dramatic GHG emissions reduction of the European building stock. To achieve scale, the information on buildings and planning processes must be improved.

1.2.2 Shift minds in your organisation by creating an approachable pilot

Municipal staff is for various reasons, including the rules of procurement, risk averse and consequently slower in adopting new technologies and innovation. Building and energy management departments are aware of the technologies used in these projects, both in theory and what has been reported in expensive light-house buildings often run by universities. But most have not seen such a building in their neighbourhood.

This project was led by innovators in their respective municipalities willing to take risks of approaching multiple systems at once. procuRE helped these leaders to convince other colleagues and departments that fossil-based heating can be replaced by tailor-made implementation of electrified heat sources such as heat pumps; that larger battery storage in building is feasible, - that multiple systems can be integrated with the use of on-site PV.

Formerly, each of these systems was considered a challenge and not sufficiently useful. Now, the integrated solution has been seen and understood driving the interest to install at least some systems with each renovation with medium-range perspective on a decarbonise building stock.

We have deliberately chosen average buildings to demonstrate replicability. Without intended it also served the purpose of being relatable and convincing. Scientifically, this effect is called the neighbourhood effect and has been also documented for in the private domain for PVs and electric cars among others.

To gain acceptance for scale utilise the neighbourhood effect. Deploy one average solution in an average building which others can relate to rather than demonstrating the edge of technology in a light-house.

1.2.3 Dramatic increase in Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) at low costs

The active deployment of systems increased the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) from an average of 20% to 66% at average total hardware and software costs of €375,000.

The SRI documents the buildings ability to utilise smart technology to increase energy efficiency, comfort and provide flexibility to the grid. The ‘smartness’ of a building refers to its ability to sense, interpret, communicate and actively respond in an efficient manner to changing conditions in relation to the operation of technical building systems, the external environment (including energy grids) and the demands from building occupants.

The values were created using the generic SRI tool provided by the European Commission (i.e. future values may change once the Member State release their own national weights for each indicator).

Smartness improves the operation of a building and the linked flexibility is essential for future grid fed mostly by RES. Capacity can be already build up at low cost as a side-effect of de-carbonisation.

1.2.4 Be creative as to what the building offers and involve occupants

Existing buildings are what they are and cannot be easily changed. They are often also not fully documented inducing risk during renovation activities. Thus, it is critical to maximise the potential whilst minimising risks.

All parties need to be creative in how to implement the system in the building and be open to finding new solutions in how to implement the necessary infrastructure. In schools, cables may not have to be hidden but show the ‘blood lines’ of the building of great interest to children. The industrial look can be leaned into using different shades and make the building look more modern without creating white sleek plaster. The localisation of new hardware can be utilised to create new functional features such as to guiding flow or providing shade. If it is expensive to lay a cable across a schoolyard, utilise antennas etc. These are just some of many examples in how the construction can be kept at cost.

Modern HVAC systems can be designed to prepare and future-proof implementation at low cost including the provision of cooling as well as scaling the power offered in a manner to be reduced in the future. For instance, an alternative is to deploy heat pumps in cascade for one device in the cascade to be removed should the envelope be tackled in the future.

A key to creative is acceptance of the occupants in involving them in the process early on. Explaining what the objective is and what may become necessary. The occupants know their building best. Aside from understanding that a certain solution has no alternatives, they may even come up with ideas.

Focus on the objective of decarbonisation rather than looks. Solutions can be practical bringing additional benefits and acceptance can be facilitated by involvement of occupants.

1.2.5 A great team effort in European fashion despite war and crisis

Horizon Europe projects require at least three Member States as part of building the Single Market, knowledge transfer and simply to build bridges. Our project represents five EU Member States, Turkey and Israel.

On our path, and as a team, we navigated an unusual high number of exogenous hits impacting the team including COVID, wars, inflation, supply shortages, earthquake, flood and national policy and cyber security changes as well as a supplier quitting the project to name the most prominent.

We stayed together with the objective insight and with the aim to finalise the project. We considered all of what happened a hit, ruffled ourselves and continue to work. We all share the believe that we live on one planet and it needs new solutions of which one we wanted and have advanced.

In this context, we also like to thank the European Union for the opportunity to try and the trust to continue allowing us to overcome the challenge and successfully deliver.

International teams are resilient. The challenging times need these opportunities to try something new and the creativity, input and varying views from each and everyone.

1.3 Structure of lessons and recommendations provided

Chapter 2 describes lessons learnt from developing and applying the core innovation of the project, i.e. de-fossilisation of buildings for any interested city aiming to replicate the effort.

Chapter 3 describes lessons learnt from implementing an innovation procurement for future procurers of innovation as well as for the EU-organisations with regard to remaining gaps of the PCP instrument.

Chapter 4 summarises the results of the cost-benefit analysis for the pilot sites and the wide-scale impact assessment for ‘active renovations’ aiming to de-fossilise buildings.

Chapter 5 provides a few recommendations for future action and policy efforts required to enable municipalities to de-fossilise the building stock faster (and deeper).

Chapter 6 provides the (updated) technical sections of the original Challenge Brief. The generic descriptions of technical challenges as well as well-tailored KPIs are being referred to and are useful basis for future procurers.

2 Insights/lessons learnt for de-fossilisation renovations

This chapter collects insights applicable to any city (or joint procurement of cities) wishing to de-fossilise their building stock.

The insights are described using the following structure:

- **Headline** stating the insight and the above classification.
- **Observation** describing the occurrence of problem and the consequence triggered, or the approach chosen as well as how the positive experience was verified.
- **Lesson** phrased as lesson learnt, mitigation strategy or considerations to take for future innovation procurements.
- **Actions/recommendations** where it may be applicable.

2.1 Planning and procurement of de-fossilisation renovation packages

In summary, to achieve a (rapid) and trouble-free renovation, thorough planning, well-designed procurement documents as well as efficient and stable relationships during the renovation are critical. The underlying questions are highly relevant as they trigger costs, effort and inefficiencies combined potentially undermining the outcome of the measure.

The lessons provided are both positive and negative experiences and state clearly what (not) to do.

2.1.1 Existing buildings are full of surprises – validate/audit your building carefully

Observation: The buildings renovated in the project have been carefully selected. They have been selected also on the basis of available information which has been shared with the suppliers to plan the site. In almost all sites we have experienced surprises. In Slovenia, the documentation of the load-bearing structure was incorrect (i.e. builders solved the construction differently to what had been planned); in Spain, the municipal piping was incorrect; in Türkiye, the specification of the local transformer station differed to what has been publicly documented.

As system integration requires stable local communication, the state, location and potential pathways for new cables, is critical. All sites experienced issues ranging from hiccups to difficulties. A hiccup may be limited to the exact location for a new bore. Difficulty arises when no physical path is possible (e.g. across a school yard) requiring additional hardware with antennas.

Lesson: Validate the final design that it is indeed doable and have (nearby) alternative solutions in mind. As soon structural issues or doubt arises, delays are almost inevitable.

2.1.2 Conduct an energy audit and include it in the planning tender

Observation: Owners of buildings have biases towards their own building. They have experienced issues over the years and give these issues priority even though it may not be the largest challenge. Similarly, contractors would like to solve all problems with what they know best. Good information is critical to select the right solution and energy audits give the context needed. In our project, dynamic models were created early in the process enabling the suppliers to scan the impacts of varying solutions and rating them against the budget the value of which diminished due to inflation and supply shortages.

Lesson: A full-scale energy audit provides a solid basis for any future planning of renovation features and dimensions. This certainty avoids the risk of emerging information and need to re-design elements of the measure. It further re-shapes how all parties think about the building and what is needed.

2.1.3 Innovative HVAC easily future-proof heating and cooling needs

Observation: Most building operators are stuck with thinking power and capacity dimensions for heating of gas and oil boilers. One does optimise for one energy rating and pick the best suitable device rated at the required power. Similarly, heat and cold are considered separate items.

Both is no longer valid when using modern HVAC. Heat pumps can satisfy both heating and cooling needs if the system is set up accordingly and existing ventilation can be readily upgraded for that purpose. They can be arranged in stages and cascades making parts of the structure flexible and removable (or upgradable) should the building need change.

Lesson: Utilise flexibility of modern HVAC to prepare both heat and cold in cascades and other opportune designs. Take into consideration future changes to the building including long-term envelop and efficiency measures to minimise or simplify future effort.

2.1.4 Construction framework contracts must cover only one legal framework

Observation: By design of an EU-grant, this project was a bundled international procurement. Thus, our suppliers had to cover several legal frameworks they were not familiar with Whilst energy efficiency is all about physics, the rules are not. Local expertise is required to apply for all necessary permits, how they need to made public or documented, and the procedures and steps differ in order across Member States. Most construction companies are SMEs. Even for large entities, most construction business is national.

As part of this R&D project we tendered by design minimally intensive renovation measures, and they still became extremely challenging in almost all legal frameworks leading to burden at the municipal entities which was supposed to be carried out by suppliers.

Thus, we strongly recommend against any attempt to bundle renovation in multiple legal frameworks as it is unknown whether companies with dependent companies in all legal frameworks will bid or succeed.

Irrespective, the concept of creating volume framework contracts for construction work must be considered a success (including the staged approach of a PCP) as the administrative aspects of tendering only occurred once (e.g. Nuremberg will trial this approach on city level, AMB has since begun conducting framework contracts for heat source replacements).

Lesson: Identify and select buildings in a given proximity bringing economies of scale to travel, site managers etc. Conduct the framework contract in stages if a performance or process is to optimised or measured initially at one building.

2.1.5 Use regulatory instruments on energy consumption and renewable energy

Observation: Legislation in Europe has advanced towards (renewable) energy communities utilising a wide range of models opening new opportunities for de-fossilisation of multiple sites at once. For instance, in Spain and Portugal it is possible to consume electric production within a radius of 2km provided both sites are equipped with smart meters and have the same owner. This is a particular

opportunity for municipalities which could equip, for instance, large schools with extensive PV-capacity and utilise the production in a nearby historic building with no means for on-site production.

Lesson: Consider the regulatory opportunities at the earliest possible stage as it implicates on the approach and scaling of hardware. In principle, think systematically about the building stock rather than each building individually.

2.1.6 Design your tender to receive turnkey services

Observation: One intent of the project is to design solutions which are replicable to other building in the believe that this will aid emerging and/or the emergence of turnkey providers. In hindsight we must consider this attempt overly ambitious especially in view of challenges of inflation and the fundamental challenge of multiple legal frameworks any such turnkey provider would have to overcome as part of the project.

We are certain that turnkey services are critical to scale the de-fossilisation renovations of (municipal) buildings as the critical staff for buildings is limited and the overhead related to buildings could be solved at scale provided the leading company has set up the necessary features.

In principle the observations of our Challenge Brief remain valid. More detail is provided in section System package design.

Lesson: Tailor your service to a strong lead contractor who is either a turnkey provider itself and / or able to confidently source (local) specialists. The lead contract must act as single point of contact to all parties and be legally responsible to deliver all parts of the service and renovation tendered.

This service should include ‘Plan IT installation, connection and testing 2.2.3’.

2.1.7 Request full set of quotes for all equipment, software and services

Observation: By design, our project had a long horizon. A few years ago, the prices for construction material were relatively stable and predictable. This situation changed and has even local dimensions with price developments souring on some Member States but not others. In addition, we observed that suppliers may overestimate their ability to forecast prices given specific circumstances and constellations. This is only natural as an active system has many components. However, forgetting any given component leads automatically to an underestimation of total costs which may require corrective action. As there was no room to increase the budget (a procedure construction companies got used to exploit) this implied re-planning or downsizing, typically, the size of storage capacity it being the most flexible and large cost item.

Lesson: Offers or bid should contain a table-based itemisation of all cost items with all prices including their source and date of sourcing. This file should become a living document from the first date of the project to which the procurer and contractor have access to. Live means that the table is updated with new prices or replaced items at all times so that the full costs are fully accessible at all times. The list serves as a checklist for cost items using status such as ‘research’, ‘offer’ and ‘ordered’. Items which have been purchased should be ticked off with the final price.

2.1.8 Consider safety, security and comfort hardware as part of initial offer

Observation: Ex-post installed heat pumps, especially larger, and batteries remain relatively unfamiliar hardware items. Whilst in new buildings, they are hidden away and designed as part of a

larger concept, existing buildings do not provide passive security through walls or noise-cancelling features. For batteries, fire risks or and protection of the devices themselves need to be considered. These issues may arise only in specific context of installation where, for instance, a wall in combination with stairs may increase the noise from heat pumps although it has been placed away from windows on purpose.

Installing fences or noise protection is in principle simple. However, doing it after the main renovation increases effort and where, for instance, concrete sealing-off ground surface is required may even trigger additional permit procedures extending the process.

Lesson: Request the contractor to foresee and budget any necessary safety security and comfort measures such as fencing or noise protection. Include procurement criteria or KPIs for noise and cite relevant legislation obliging the contractor to deliver the necessary equipment should the renovation fail to meet this criteria.

2.1.9 Validate technical features are truly provided by selected hardware

Observation: The capacity for interoperability of hardware suppliers and the system integration market overall remains immature. For instance, basic features proved to be missing (e.g. dynamic control of heat pumps and settings not provided by some suppliers) or insufficiently implemented (e.g. specific requirements including specific hardware needed to operate standardised communication protocols). It appears that interoperability implementation is achieved by not implementing the protocol but by “making it work” with some piece of hardware which may itself not fully implement the standard. Functions appear to be added as requested even if they limit or hinder full utilisation of otherwise excellent specifications. Many resellers as well as the hardware providers seem to be unaware of these limitations neither citing them in their documentation and manuals nor able to respond or adopt quickly.

The consequences are that sourcing may have to be repeated or extended, communication with suppliers implemented or even worse the operation approach for a building adopted to the functions available.

Lesson: Do not rely on manual or documentation alone. For large or expensive hardware utilise existing discussion boards or seek information about a nearby site operating the system to exchange with a user in a similar situation that critical requirements are met.

2.2 Implementation/operation of de-fossilisation renovations / building integration

2.2.1 Clearly identify the supervision of the (active) renovation

Observation: The R&D procuRE project attempted to reshape the distribution of responsibility surrounding planning and implementation of a site. Whilst it was hindered by cross-border travel including through the limitations of war, the allocation of responsibility was not always fully adopted by our suppliers. What we observed is that the planning entities would ultimately run into a situation where they are both client and contractor. Although, in monetary values, active renovations itself was small, the impact of replacing and readjusting heating and cooling systems has large implications on operational costs. Thus, the job does not end with physical installation but also

requires monitoring and optimising until the site runs at efficient levels if ICT-solutions are not able to take over this role.

Lesson: Appoint an independent construction supervision to check implementation and performance of the site representing the interests of the client even if not mandatory by law given the volume or nature of the renovation. If multiple sites are being renovated, this can be implemented as part of a framework contract.

2.2.2 Plan logistics, especially on tight locations

Observation: Our renovations did not require scaffolding or large quantities of material. However, heat pumps, PV and some batteries are large and heavy items which need lifting onto roofs or careful positioning often requiring cranes or other machinery. Furthermore, the installation is not necessarily completed in one day whilst the entire equipment is usually delivered in one day requiring physical storage space which may also have to protect the equipment.

Lesson: Validate the necessary volume and requirements for storage well in advance. Clear the necessary spaces and validate access is sufficient for material and machinery. Where public spaces are utilised, seek the necessary permits.

2.2.3 Plan IT installation, connection and testing

Observation: Dependency on legacy hardware in buildings as well as the connection to existing large-scale or city-wide energy management systems remains challenging and work-intensive. Relevant aspects to consider are IP addresses, linkups, IT security including the need for and specification of VPNs. In context of city-wide systems security and network settings are a particular challenge as it introduces another external bottleneck (e.g. the responsible staff). The process and all requirements should be transparently documented which may, for the first time, require requesting the relevant department to create a transparent and accessible guidance useful for external parties.

Suppliers having selected hardware and software should be held responsible to stitch all components together and validate the proper function. Like electric vehicles, a smart building is nothing without properly functioning software. This process has taken much longer than we anticipated and has not been sufficiently appreciated by suppliers in their planning.

Lesson: Hardware and software must be part of planning and the implementation period a strict component of the overall schedule with clear timelines near completion of the physical installation. Any changes needed to the infrastructure (e.g. cables, new connectors) must be part of the renovation and not an afterthought.

2.2.4 Test what else your system is capable of (e.g. black start capacity)

Observation: During the project, Eilat was hit by war. Suddenly, some unintended features of our renovation became relevant. The installation in Eilat has already been tested to be fully capable of black starting the building and contributing to restoring the local grid. The smartness of the building increases the resilience of the city.

Lesson: Once installed and fully operational, check which new requirements your solutions may be able to meet given the flexibility of active systems.

2.2.5 Implement performance based indicators

Observation: During the design of the Challenge Brief it became apparent that most widely used indicators are static or focused on performance of envelopes. The performance of active systems requires aligning timely dimensions of production and consumption of energy as well as the overall utilisation of on-site energy.

Lesson: Tender with and utilise for monitoring suitable indicators to measure the performance of the system. We recommend our indicators developed for the Challenge Brief which have also been used to assess the performance of the sites in deliverable D7.5. The indicators are documented in section 6.2.

2.2.6 Plan user training as part of the renovation

Observation: The co-creation of innovative RES solutions exploiting smartness applications requires that on-site professionals involved in everyday operations (even including subcontractor staff) and procurers' staff monitoring building performance can access user-friendly and engaging training materials with the aim of exploiting tools' potential to the extent possible. The prioritisation of the renovation activities is understood in the context of testing an innovative co-created solution, which may demand ad-hoc attention (e.g. from the orders' placement and subsequent customs clearance procedures to ensuring the actual delivery and the final adjustments during the installation process). Still, a user-centred training approach is considered paramount in ensuring that the solution's potential fully materialises (and opportunities to enhance performance can be identified) by fostering curiosity among engaged professionals in charge of running the building's operation.

Lesson: Plan user training activities as a fixed stage of the renovation project. Operators and occupants will notice that the building changed and should not have to wait to get the necessary training to use the building efficiently. Not doing so undermines the acceptance of the renovation and may lead unintended behaviour which would become routing without training.

2.3 Risk summary for consideration in future projects

procuRE was impacted by an unusual number of exogenous shocks including geo-political events, market shocks, national as well as project related events as well as being the first PCP to be directly affected by particularities of (complex) European VAT law. While the consortium and the suppliers have overcome most of these challenges and were able to complete the project, we wish to share the list which may serve as potential template for risk assessment. Where applicable, the lessons learnt from these challenges are linked and described in the following sections.

- Geo-political and market shocks
 - COVID pandemic during project start, tender preparation and tender;
 - During the tender was public, emergence of the first supply chain and price volatility crisis in the construction sector (as result of COVID and impassable Suez Canal, etc.), reducing the time available for companies to bid and resulting in lower than anticipated bid numbers;
 - During renovation planning, deepening supply crisis and inflation shocks due to the Ukraine war resulting in higher than planned costs which required adaption of the renovation packages;

- During implementation prolonged non-availability of critical components including heat pumps and batteries linked to the shortage and worsened by the chip crises.
- During implementation, challenges related to the acquisition of commercial offers and contracting. All sites have been struggling to secure contracts with all necessary subcontractors and to ensure the delivery of all necessary equipment within the price cap determined by the project. As an EU-project, premium payments were not possible. This is mainly caused by the supply crisis linked to the Ukraine-Russian war and the strong price increases due to inflation.
- During implementation, start of the war in Israel with supplier staff having to turn-around on the airport of Tel Aviv. Aside from the obvious impact on staff, the municipality of Eilat hosts many displaced Israelis, effectively doubling the population and exacerbating workforce limitations for many employers. Being the southernmost city in Israel, it was vulnerable to the risk of air raids.
- European framework
 - VAT framework is not suitable joined pre-commercial procurements innovating on tangible local assets. The effort to stay compliant was immense for lead procurer, procurers, suppliers and even subcontractors with differing and changing opinions across Member States. The core lesson is to not centralise the budget in such procurements and let each procurer pay invoices based on the local rules even if it means higher efforts on project level.
- National events
 - In Slovenia, major flooding in August 2023 and the resulting impacts including local damages and delays of long-planned grid measures;
 - In Israel, re-allocation of the demonstration site in Eilat due to termination of national funding for additional work planned. Resolved through rapid application of the Renovation Approach to the newly allocated building.
 - In Türkiye decision to cut all external VPN connection requiring dedicated networks and additional setups of BMS.
- Project-related events
 - Low number of applications removing an element of competition during the first two phases.
 - Attempt of a supplier to renegotiate the terms which led to the exclusion but impacted the sites allocation and implementations of the Renovation Packages.
 - Complications of the Annex 7 signatures due to local accounting rules (this requirement has been removed for PCPs under the Horizon Europe programme).

3 Guidance on innovation procurement / PCPs

This section presents our insights from having implemented the PCP. Practical recommendations on how to implement a PCP and reflections on the instrument in general.

3.1 Insights after completion of the PCP

The following lessons focus on our general perception of innovation procurement. Please also consider the structural challenge of cross-border procurement of tangible items due to current VAT rules which we strongly recommend against doing (see 3.3.1 for detail).

3.1.1 Innovations are complex, tackle one innovation at a time

Observation: EU grants are driven by opportunity of the topic. Thus, our proposal and subsequent Challenge Brief has been partly shaped in what would be ideal to fully succeed in line with the call. We must recognise that our Challenge Brief attempted to seek one too many solutions. We attempted to both improve a complex process as well as the output of the process using in part novel methodologies.

The output of the process and methods applied, we consider successful it being the Renovation Packages and thus the sites documented in D7.5 in detail. As described in our success stories this approach is a viable way forward to dramatically reduce GHG emissions in the European building stock within a short timeframe. The usual limitations of material, staff availability and increasingly cost (overruns) for envelope renovations and extended duration binding staff to a single building do not apply. The buildings have proven to deliver the GHG emission savings at positive socio-economic costs (despite many orders having been placed during extraordinary times).

The evolution of the process, however, was only satisfactory in that it delivered the project but insufficient to be repeated. The issue is partly structural due to delivering services in multiple legal frameworks (see section 2.1.4) each bringing different requirements which are difficult to integrate. Instead, a dedicated IT project would be required to focus the development on a versatile platform. Since the Renovation Packages had to progress and were the critical milestone, the development of the process on how to document and organise small decisions to come later, became an afterthought rather than the first step from which benefits would only emerge at a later stage. A dedicated project would also have been required as it would require the suppliers to approach the IT challenge with an open mind and without the anticipation of being affected by changing the dynamic in how client and contractors interact.

Lesson: Be ambitious but consider whether multiple innovations may compete for the attention of both supplier and the procurer. In doubt, consider splitting the efforts in lots hereby creating parallel and independent work streams which can be assessed separately.

Remark: As operators of a large building stock, we still have a deep need for better working arrangements with contractors and documentation of buildings (see also 5.3). Nuremberg is soon starting an effort to develop a solution in German context and we, as a consortium, are working on a future project for a transferrable solution.

3.1.2 Not all ideas for R&D and innovation will work but positive surprises occur

Observations: As described in the prior paragraph’s challenges may arise and not all elements of the research effort will succeed. It took a lot of time to mitigate the unforeseen aspects, particularly, the VAT challenge and the need for adjusting initial plans due to inflation. For most of the project, we were aware which elements could be better and tried in intensive exchange with suppliers to improve the process of planning and implementing the sites without succeeding fully.

To see success, is more difficult. In preparation of finalising the project we met in person, and we discovered many unexpected success stories. Our project has already shifted many minds including occupants and other colleagues, having delivered the hardware and intended savings. But it achieved more including a surprisingly large increase in SRI score as well as very good cost-benefit assessment. The hardware is often capable of more than we thought (e.g. black start ability) and we are optimistic to find further surprises and improve operation during the extended course of operating the buildings.

Lesson: What does not work is obvious. Do not forget to analyse the outcome for the success achieved. There will be much more than you originally thought.

3.1.3 Innovation procurements are a good path to solve practical challenges

Observation: PCP topics bring the rare opportunity to analyse the challenge before taking decisive action (i.e. releasing the tender). The European Commission and agencies are invited to consider the proposal as a first stage of the tender to come. Only through analysis will it be possible to design the optimal challenge. There must be room to improve the initial proposal potentially substituting initial elements with other more critical or better integrated aspects.

Lesson: As identified above, we have been in part too ambitious in our approach partly dictated from what we have proposed. In the future, we will re-assess all aspects for feasibility and maximum impact. If necessary, we will suggest an amendment to the Description of Action in order to keep the tender and the grant aligned.

3.2 Practical lesson on implementation of a PCP

This section focuses on the instrument of innovation procurement and pre-commercial procurement. Due to its unique setup, procuRE is able to share lessons on what (not) to do. Some lessons were surprises, even for [empirica](#) – the PCP expert partner in this project – which has been in a central role in numerous PCPs at different stages of development ([ProEmpower](#), [HSMonitor](#), [procuRE](#), [IncareHeart](#), [IprocureSecurity](#), [CircularPSP](#), [Dynamo](#), suHCO).

The section does not wish to reproduce already available guidance such as provided through the [EAFIP toolkit](#) and therefore does not repeat widely documented steps if procuRE is not contributing any additional insight. Vis-à-vis this section may serve as a source to document for future iterations of the EAFIP toolkit and training as well as future iterations of the PCP instrument for the EC.

3.2.1 Align evaluation criteria, Challenge Brief and tender template structure

Observation: Once procuRE defined the evaluation criteria, the structure of the Challenge Brief was fully aligned with the Challenge Brief. For instance, all technical sub-criteria were grouped in the “technical section” of the Challenge Brief. Further, each sub-criteria comprised a heading and a

second-level heading. This approach was also mirrored to the technical template as displayed in the table below.

Evaluation Sub-criteria	Challenge Brief	Technical Template
T1 – Technical Sub-criterion 1	1.1 T1 – Technical Sub-criterion 1	1.1 T1 – Technical Sub-criterion 1
T2 – Technical Sub-criterion 2	1.2 T2 – Technical Sub-criterion 2	1.2 T2 – Technical Sub-criterion 2
C1 – Commercial Sub-criterion 1	2.1 C1 – Commercial Sub-criterion 1	2.1 C1 – Commercial Sub-criterion 1

The advantages for tenderers and procurers are that all parties know where the requirements are described, where to describe the response in the proposal and how many points the response will contribute to the overall score.

Benefits were observed during the design of the Challenge Brief and during evaluation since there was nearly no confusion as to where tenderers have placed the information relevant for any given section of the Challenge Brief. By conclusion, the tenderers also had less effort during the drafting of their proposals.

Lesson: Structure the Challenge Brief well and align it with technical tender template. Consider that tenderers are investing time. The less time they need to sort information from the RfT the more time is spent on the content of the proposal or the more tenderers consider it worthwhile to submit a proposal.

3.2.2 Include all technical content – even work processes – into the technical section

Observation: The procuRE Challenge Brief tackles two core innovations: the integration of a wide range of building systems into one coherent, systemic and generic Renovation Approach and the coordination of procurers and suppliers in designing a specific Renovation Package from the Approach for any given building through the process of Co-Design which, however, requires also integrating technical innovations such as platforms, information sharing and tools.

With the intent of separating the issues more clearly, the two areas of innovation were split across the technical and the project management sections since Co-Design mostly reflects a work process. It appears that for some tenderers the Co-Design procedure was an afterthought insufficiently well integrated with the Renovation Approach. The reason might have been that Co-Design was made part of the project management section implying that it is limited to the duration of the project whilst the consortium clearly expected it to be a lasting achievement.

Lesson: Whilst it is important to clearly separate technical and process innovations, both should be presented as part of the technical section. The project management section should only contain content which is limited to the implementation of the project itself and not include innovation results expected from the tenderer to last beyond the project.

3.2.3 Wide Open Market Consultation critical in light of external shocks

Observation: procuRE conducted very wide reaching and repeated Open Market Consultation (OMC) events. The project has recorded over 50 registered entities on the match-making platform and over 20 intends to submit a proposal until the late summer of 2021.

Unfortunately, just before the launch of the tender, the supply crisis hit the construction sector. The parties expected to tender were suddenly occupied with securing materials for their ongoing and upcoming projects with procuRE suddenly representing a long-term consideration in a very volatile market. The price shocks were so extreme that it was suddenly unclear whether the PCP budget was sufficient despite careful planning during the proposal and refinement during the design of the Challenge Brief including anticipated cost increases.

As a result, the number of offers was unexpectedly low despite two extensions of the proposal submission deadline. Multiple offers had to be rejected due to obvious formal errors. Formal errors are a clear indication of how much time or resources were spent on the proposal and on these cases it was clearly not enough.

An extensive Open Market Consultation ensured that procuRE received a sufficient number of offers despite the difficult circumstances. Had the project not invested the effort on national and international level, sharing recordings and inviting to tender training events, the number of offers might have been smaller and the procedure would have had to be cancelled.

Lesson: Plan your OMCs wide and consider each one equally important even if it appears to be repetitive. Spend considerable resources in approaching the local market. Identify the actors which could be able to deliver the solution and those who would be able to build a successful consortium.

3.2.4 Risk departments can cause delays in implementation-heavy PCPs)

This factor is only likely to apply where implementation of PCP solutions requires local specialised effort which cannot be provided through the R&D suppliers themselves and/or significant amount of equipment. The factor has been exasperated by the initial supply crisis and the additional impact of the Russian invasion of Ukraine the of the effects of which were ongoing in April-July 2023.

Observation: Multiple observations must be noted to fully appreciate the issue at hand:

- procuRE innovations need to be demonstrated in buildings which requires implementation of a wide range of systems including equipment through multiple specialised local companies.
- Since only one of the two suppliers can change any given buildings, the sites were split during evaluation of the call-off for phase III (each supplier was allocated three buildings).
- Suppliers learn whether and which sites they have been allocated after evaluation of phase III not being able to take any preparatory steps prior.
- Local companies can only be selected once the site has been allocated for practical reasons:
 - Multiple competing suppliers would approach the same limited number of local companies with an unspecified target date of which most contracts would fall through representing an immense administrative burden for suppliers and local companies and if contracted as subcontractors the project partners.
 - These local companies are not involved in the creation of the innovation itself during phases I and II.
- The selection of local companies is also linked to the acquisition of equipment (e.g. PV panels, HVAC, sensors and control systems) as specified by the Renovation Package for any given site. These prices have been extremely volatile in recent years.

- Since local companies and sourcing of equipment prices needs to be conducted one by one, the entire chain of any site is limited by the slowest moving part. At the same time, offers are usually time-limited.

Whilst above listed observations can cause delays in itself, the combination of delayed information (i.e. certainty of being chosen) and high volatility (i.e. process for local companies and equipment) can become a critical issue for risk management departments within suppliers. Such departments sign-off projects only once a certain degree of information and certainty has been reached.

As a consequence, not only was one site affected but the entire basket of three sites was limited by the slowest moving offer needed to receive approval to sign off on the specific contract for phase III. By extension this did not affect only one but both suppliers.

It must be noted that procurers aided suppliers by sourcing an initial list of relevant local companies made available during phase II and aided during site-visits with local companies as well as reminding local companies to provide (complete) offers as well as through verification of details which might have gone lost on translation between two or three languages.

Ultimately, procuRE was able to source all required prices despite a significant shortage in heat pumps.

Lesson: The recommendation is a significant preparation gap between phase II and phase III if the above circumstances also apply. It is critical to require suppliers to clearly disclose all information on the state of sourcing in order to be able to identify gaps across demonstration sites which need to be focused on. Weekly status calls with the lead procurer are recommended. In preparation, information on local companies should be sourced and shared as early as possible.

3.3 Instrument related lessons to be solved on EU-level / require mitigation

The following challenges address the innovation procurement instrument and can only be resolved on EU-level. In the meantime, projects need to consider this lesson and address them in their implementation.

3.3.1 Procurement requirements and VAT are key factors for choosing the Lead Procurer

Observation: The PCP-FAQ provided by the European Commission highlights to select a Lead Procurer where VAT-rules allow for a cheap procurement. However, another important aspect are the procurement requirements which might differ for joint procurement compared to traditional procurement.

In the case of procuRE, KSSENA took on the role as Lead Procurer. Slovenia has implemented very strict procedural requirements for joint public procurements including the publication in national platforms, opening and documentation procedures. As a consequence it was necessary to contract a professional procurement solution and consultants helping to setup the platform correctly to be also in line with the requirements of the PCP-procedure. The implied costs were not foreseen during the proposal as it was anticipated that empirica would be able to implement the procedure used in prior PCPs.

Regardless of selecting the ideal Lead Procurer on paper, it must be noted that few procurers are willing to lead a joint European procurement. Hence, the other procurers need to accept the conditions at the Lead Procurer and should tolerate any additional burden or costs incurred by the Lead Procurer even if these appear unreasonable compared to their local circumstances.

Lesson: Clarify early how the procurement will be publicly launched and what the local requirements are specifically. With regard to VAT, clarify early which rules apply and whether they are likely to remain stable until publication of the tender as a change of rules will have implications on the tender budget.

3.3.2 Non-acceptance of negative interest rates is a significant burden for PCP coordinators

Observation: The pre-financing structure of PCPs is unusual. Beginning of the second project year, coordinators receive almost the entire PCP-subcontracting budget the majority of which will only be spent around two years later when the third phase of the PCP is running. In the meantime, the coordinator has to keep hold of the money. During 2021 and 2022, before inflation, the interest rates were negative implying costs for the coordinator which are not eligible. Despite picking the bank with the most favourable conditions, the coordinator accumulated negative interest for 20 months.

procuRE intended to mitigate the issue by requesting a third pre-payment for Phase 3 PCP budget reducing the accumulation of negative interest which was rejected.

Lesson: Identify the bank with the most favourable conditions.

Recommendation to EC: Negative interest rates should be accepted as costs mirroring the requirement to document positive interest rate which are deducted from future EC payments. The same rule should also be applied in reverse.

3.3.3 Co-Funding requirement of Horizon 2020 is an administrative burden (resolved)

This factor can be considered resolved through changes made to PCPs in Horizon Europe.

Observation: procuRE is a Horizon2020 project. Under H2020 conditions, 90% of the funding was provided by the Horizon2020 Programme and 10% were to be contributed by the procurers themselves. These terms were known during proposal. However, during the preparation of the request for tender, the Contracting Authority required an Annex confirming that the co-funding amount stands ready for payments of suppliers.

The financial department in one local administration, however, had to consider this additional document as an additional requirement outside of the context of the grant agreement based on local law. This situation was further complicated through the already completed centralisation shifting the 90%-funding to the lead procurer. The local law requires that any expenditure is fully budgeted and foreseen following a very rigid risk assessment approach. Hence, despite the contribution of the H2020 Programme, the full amount would have to be budgeted, the financial department could not do without the necessary votes in parliament.

The complications were ultimately resolved by adding a number of sentences to Annex 7 without modifying the original statement of Annex 7, something the Contracting Authority was –

understandably – unwilling to change. The entire process delayed the publication of the tender by two months causing a considerable delay for the entire project and all partners.

Lesson: Begin any formal approval processes as early as possible even if it appears early. This typically includes the procurement agreement and any annexes required by the Contracting Authority.

Recommendation to EC: The change to 100% funding of PCP-subcontracting is welcome and does remove considerable administrative burden from all project partners and the departments to be involved.

4 CBA and wide-scale impact assessment

The section summarises the modelling results from the sensitive D7.6 deliverable making the core aspects public.

4.1 Overview of the Assessment Approach

This section presents the large-scale impact assessment conducted to evaluate the potential across the European building stock. The content is based on Chapter 3 of Deliverable D7.6. The impact assessment consists of site-specific cost-benefit analysis and a large-scale impact assessment for large portfolio holders and EU-wide impact. To ensure consistency and comparability, the modelling applies a common time horizon up to 2050, reflecting both the expected lifetime of the core “active” technologies and the European Union’s long-term climate targets. A “cautious and conservative” modelling approach was applied throughout, meaning assumptions were intentionally restrained to avoid overestimating benefits. The cost-benefit tool compares two scenarios.

(1) Do Nothing Scenario: Reflects current energy use and costs without new interventions and reflects the baseline

(2) Intervention Scenario: Represents the investment in and impact of procuRE’s active renovation solutions.

The comparison between these two provides insight into when and how the investment “pays off” in economic and environmental terms. Results are calculated over time and adjusted to present value using a 4% discount rate, which reflects the time value of money.

4.2 Key Inputs and Assumptions

The analysis used detailed data from each pilot site, harmonised where possible for comparability:

Energy Use and Renewables: The study measured consumption of oil, gas, and electricity before and after interventions, along with renewable energy generated on-site. Supply chain disruptions meant some planned battery installations were delayed, but current market conditions now make equal or better energy performance achievable at the same cost.

Carbon Emission Factors: Standard European values were applied to calculate CO₂-equivalent emissions from oil, gas, and electricity, reflecting national energy mixes.

Renewable Share of National Grids: Each country’s electricity mix already includes a growing renewable share (ranging from 14% in Eilat to 73% in Gaia), assumed to increase by 1% per year.

Energy Prices and Future Trends: Energy prices were based on Eurostat data, with modest annual increases projected above inflation (2% for oil/gas, 1% for electricity).

Societal Cost of Emissions: Each tonne of avoided CO₂ was valued at €300, increasing by 2% per year. This captures the broader economic benefit of reduced emissions (e.g., improved health and environmental outcomes).

Income Streams: Potential future income from renewable feed-in tariffs or carbon certificates was not included, keeping the model conservative.

For detailed information on data sources and conversion factors, see D7.6.

4.3 Results Across procuRE Pilot Sites (to 2050)

Capital Expenditure (CAPEX): Total intervention investment across all six sites was about €2.25 million, or roughly €375,000 per site. After accounting for depreciation and replacements, this equates to an additional €260,000 investment per site compared to doing nothing (baseline).

Operating Costs (OPEX): The total operational costs, excluding energy expenses, amounted to approximately €11,000 in the baseline scenario and €20,500 after the intervention. This corresponds to an increase in average day-to-day operational costs from €1,850 to €3,400 per site, mainly due to the additional maintenance requirements of the newly installed photovoltaic systems, batteries, and electrical components.

Energy Costs and Savings: Energy-related operational costs decreased significantly from €3.07 million in the baseline to €2.02 million after intervention. This represents an average reduction of about one-third in total energy expenditure across sites.

Greenhouse Gas Emissions (GHG): The interventions are expected to directly avoid around 4,175 tonnes of CO₂ equivalent by 2050, with an additional 1,873 tonnes avoided indirectly through cleaner electricity grids. In total, this corresponds to approximately 6,000 tonnes of avoided emissions, a major contribution to local and EU climate objectives.

Economic and Societal Results: While direct financial results (from an investor's perspective) were slightly negative in most sites, except in Istanbul and Eilat, where energy prices are higher, the socio-economic balance was strongly positive.

When the wider benefits of reducing emissions are included, the interventions deliver over twice the value of their costs, confirming that active renovation is a cost-effective strategy for decarbonisation. Even when considering only EU-based sites, the overall result remains positive, demonstrating that such measures are economically and environmentally beneficial when societal impacts are taken into account.

4.4 Scaling the Results to the European Level

To estimate the broader potential, the findings were extrapolated to represent typical European office and school buildings, together forming a building stock of approximately 4.18 million units across the EU. This includes an estimated 780,000 educational buildings and 3.4 million office buildings, of which only a small fraction currently achieve zero-emission standards.

Using average data from the pilot sites:

- An **average building** would require an investment of about **€375,000**, resulting in a **financial loss of €174,000** but a **positive socio-economic benefit of €415,000**.
- Each renovated building could **avoid approximately 734 tonnes of CO₂e** by 2050.

Three scenarios have been calculated to display the potential of active renovations:

- Municipalities invest in 1,000 buildings at full cost.
- Municipalities invest €1 billion at full cost.
- Municipalities receive €1 billion to compensate financial loss.

For the third scenario it is assumed that a third party such as national governments or the EU provides grants to cities to incentives the investment. Given most of the non-residential building stock is owned by cities, this may be a necessary step to achieve climate goals.

Table: Impact assessment of scaled procuRE-CBA under the developed scenarios

Indicator	1,000 Buildings	1 billion investment	Financial loss cover
Buildings renovated	1,000	2,667	5,740
Investment (million EUR)	375	1,000	2,152
National/EU costs (mEUR)	-	-	1,000
Energy costs avoided (mEUR)	114	303	653
Municipal financial result (mEUR)	-174	-465	0
Socio-economic result (mEUR)	416	1,109	2,386
GHG emissions avoided (tCO ₂ e)	734,147	1,958,073	4,213,727

4.5 Opportunities to increase impact

Further improvements in financial performance and overall impact could be achieved by expanding the range of revenue and cost-reduction mechanisms available to municipalities. For example, enabling access to feed-in tariffs, carbon certificates, or compensation for providing flexibility to the electricity grid could help generate additional income streams and shorten payback periods. Moreover, the adoption of framework contracts and integrated procurement models can further reduce investment costs and streamline processes, as demonstrated by pilot cities such as Barcelona and Nuremberg.

To drive many renovations, action-linked direct support to cities achieves high carbon savings. For instance, developing joint financing approaches where municipalities and national or EU authorities share the investment costs offers a viable pathway to accelerate renovation while ensuring that both local and society benefits from reduced emissions and progress toward shared climate goals.

4.6 Key Messages for procurers

Active renovation—combining renewable energy systems, smart building controls, and electrification—offers municipalities a highly effective means of reducing both carbon emissions and long-term energy costs. Although the initial investments are significant, the socio-economic returns are clearly positive, confirming that such measures are cost-effective when wider societal benefits are considered. Policy and financial support at national or EU level can play a crucial enabling role, allowing cities to invest in decarbonising their building stock now and to contribute meaningfully to achieving the European Union’s zero-emission targets by 2050.

5 Policy Recommendations

In addition, we have developed a set of specific **policy recommendations** from the municipal perspective. The recommendations aim to enable further build on the project.

The insights are described using the following structure:

- **Background** describing relevant information to understand the context of the recommendation.
- **Insights from procuRE** providing data and information to assess the recommendation.
- **Recommendation/request** describing the desired action.

5.1 Support municipalities to de-fossilise the building stock

Background

The recommendation builds on the model and results presented in chapter 4.

Municipal/regional needs and insights (procuRE project)

Based on energy prices and the costs experienced during the project, the deployment of active renovations is currently a financial loss for municipalities. Utilising the average European building modelled in our cost-benefit analysis and considering the investment of €375,000 leads to similar performance improvements, the discounted financial loss until 2050 is around €174,000. This investment would avoid 734 tCO₂e equal to avoided social costs of GHG of €589,800 or a positive net socio-socio-economic benefit of €415,600.

In some Member States the result may be even better as feed-in tariffs or, even better, net-metering allows to substitute energy costs across temporal duration (i.e. from summer to winter) or spatial dimension (i.e. in another building owned by the municipality).

The result could improve further if GHG certificates or the ability to provide flexibility to the local grid would be available.

Recommendation/Request

Municipalities should be incentivised to also de-fossilise the buildings with average performance and with no urgent need to modernise or renovate the envelope. As it stands, the financial result requires compensation to truly achieve scale.

National governments and the EU are asked to provide grants covering the financial loss to municipalities to deploy active renovations in their building stock. The approach could be facilitated by deploying a building-specific model along the lines of our cost-benefit analysis covering:

- Current energy demand and standardised energy prices for the building,
- Income which could be generated from the installations,
- A limited time-scale,
- A fixed budget for the investment linked to performance factors,
- A sharing factor between municipality and payer based on the financial situation of the administration.

The scale for covering the financial loss can be bound to the energetic success, in particular GHG emission reduction, and could be deployed via ESCO models and organisations to grow and diversify

the market. Current ESCOs, however, have no incentive to approach system integration as they seek buildings with minimal risks in terms of energetic performance (i.e. envelope renovations).

The model can be updated yearly regarding the average prices of requirement equipment, the to the expected energetic performance and energy price levels with minimal effort.

The effort could theoretically be combined with and industrial strategy to scale EU-domestic production of the relevant equipment.

5.2 Research on ‘system focused renovation’ (efficiency, electrification renewables, smartness) as means towards a zero-emission building stock

Background

The background is the same as described in the introduction. This recommendation builds on the lessons learnt and described above as means to drive this approach to economies of scale.

Municipal/regional needs and insights (procuRE project)

The procuRE project underpins the EC policy for zero-emission buildings by aiming to lift many buildings to the optimal efficiency level and remove fossil dependency through maximising on-site RES production and optimising self-sufficiency through system integration and smartness without intervention in building fabric. The project deploys a replicable Renovation Approach capable of delivering the highest possible renewable energy supply to an existing non-residential building with adequate envelope quality at affordable costs.

An increasing number of cities, regions and other owners of major building portfolios wish to achieve fossil-free buildings by 2035/2040 (e.g. Nuremberg need to switch 120 buildings from gas to heat pumps). There are an estimated 780,000 educational buildings and 3.4 million offices in the EU⁶. Only 9% of non-residential buildings are already nZEB.

Building departments and energy agencies in municipalities are unable to deliver the necessary scope of renovations due to a lack of capacity (staff including specialists) and the complexity of renovation processes (including the increasing number of technologies). The suggested approaches bring the following advantages to cities and the wider European industry:

- De-fossilisation completed within a couple of months and at low costs of €50-220 Euro per square meter for buildings greater than 2,000 m² and 500 Euro/m² for a 700 m² office. (i.e. no lengthy measures to the envelope).
- Economies of scale are utilised as most effort is occurring off-site at industrial scale (e.g. production of PV and storage, ready-to-install preparation of BACs and devices)
- Capacity of trades and city resources are freed up to focus on inefficient buildings requiring time-consuming envelope measures (i.e. planning, permits, construction) with low impact are avoided;

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/energy/eu-buildings-database_en

- Integrating complex systems (e.g. HVAC, fresh air, RES, storage, BACS), increasing efficiency, users' comfort and other Smart-Ready Indicator (SRI⁷) linked benefits.
- Reduction of environmental impact and material waste.
- Facilitation of rapid turnkey offers with great potential for ESCOs linking incentives to fossil-free building operation.

Evidence on the implementation of the active renovation approach is currently being collected in six non-residential buildings (three schools and three offices).

Recommendation/Request

Establish “specific consumption curves” of building stock for Member States and conduct research into the potential of eliminating fossil fuel consumption through high-impact efficiency gains, smartness, RES and storage with focus on small and medium sized buildings.

The current version of DEEP⁸ does not map measures covering smartness, storage and RES hereby excluding a wide range of technologically available options. Since financial institutions are notoriously averse to complexity – it being perceived as risk – system focused renovations considering the building as a whole are unlikely to gather funding. Partner EURAC has conducted research for an PPP which could be included.

One-stop-shops will be able to understand the local market conditions including prices, delays due to labour or material shortages. To minimise emissions in the local building stock and integrate with the heating and cooling plants, one-stop-shops need a larger set of tools. They require guidance on how to identify buildings with adequate efficiency which could be suitable for a system renovation approach utilising high-impact efficiency, electrification, renewables and storage. Further, they will require guidance and training as well as communication means to explain such novel approach.

Suggested Instruments (any): Technical or feasibility study or fitness check, JRC paper. Alternatively, a large CSA aiming for a large base.

5.3 Develop a commissioning/project solution for municipalities to procure, coordinate, deploy and operate large number of renovations (with upgrade potential for one-stop-shops)

Background

Currently, operators of public building encounter huge difficulties when procuring a renovation or the necessary services and are therefore forced to buy-in and sometimes coordinate services and works increasing the number of possible points of failure. For decades, renovation projects have been suffering from coordination and communication breakdowns leading to additional effort required.

The current situation is overburdening to cities and regions in terms of resources and the expertise required to be kept in-house. As a result, fewer renovations are planned and conducted delaying the ambitions of cities to become carbon-neutral and to lead by example.

⁷ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/smart-readiness-indicator_en

⁸ <https://deep.ec.europa.eu/>

During renovations, the devil is in the detail (e.g. is each element load-bearing, can cables go across a surface, is there sufficient space, access during school holidays). Any such questions should only be answered once reliably and not hold up work. This requires clear structures, processes and communication on both sides.

Insights from procuRE

The pre-commercial procurement attempted to trigger innovation in this critical area as a secondary objective. Unfortunately, the suppliers have not delivered sufficient innovation in this regard. The reason are connected to the fact that the incentives and needs of suppliers (i.e. the party developing the renovation) and procurers (i.e. cities) are not aligned. There is no benefit for suppliers to disclose intermediate steps and planning or make all calculations and iterations traceable even if proactive procurers would be enabled to improve the process, avoid or flag possible errors and added costs down the line. The current experience has and will remain to induce immense efficiency losses in time and costs which cannot be utilised for another renovation. In this context, the procuRE project has repeatedly assessed BIM solutions which, at this stage, are too complex, incomplete and expensive for renovation projects in average size buildings.

This paper argues that cities need better tools for project management of renovation projects. Current tools are biased towards the needs of contractors which results in outsourcing of effort and inefficient use of time in the responsible departments.

A dedicated and specialised tool for basic multi-stakeholder project management of renovations (or simplified and extended BIM) is required which is able to cover organisational and procedural aspects of planning, exchanging on and implementing a renovation. An efficient, effective, and reliable commissioning solution includes at least the following:

- One-face to the customer approach
- Clarity on responsibilities and timing from design to implementation
- A process for information requests from supplier to procurer ensuring minimal friction and effort
- Regular exchange meetings in which suppliers inform the procurers about the most recent version of the Renovation Package and state of work
- Decision making tools based on relevant information and the documentation in Renovation Packages
- Regarding data
 - A near live working repository for all related files including intermediate iterations
 - Transparency on the most recent version and all recent changes to the Renovation Package aiding quick orientation by procurers
 - Where possible and utilised integration and links to BIM models or other tools
- In addition, the following features are desirable after commissioning was completed:
 - Interactive training and upskilling materials for building operators
 - Tracking of performance against KPIs
 - Reasoning for divergence from performance targets including cost estimates
 - Transparency on operating and maintenance costs
 - Analysis of impact of occupant behaviour, unused potentials, and the utilisation of education
 - Predictive maintenance

- Recommendations for mitigation and / or optimisation measures

Recommendation/Request

Support development of a commissioning, two-sided project management tool (building on existing frameworks) for public organisations and/or support co-development of simplified BIM solutions with cities (i.e. not those targeting high-yield new built projects), which the cities can customise and enforce onto renovation contractors. The tool should be globally installable or provided via a platform at low costs. It needs to be applied and tested during regular renovation processes. It should be scalable permitting testing by parties not at the core of requirement collection and use case design. Any emerging solution is likely to benefit the entire renovation market.

Potential to deploy in one-stop-shop: Once developed and tested, the solution could also be deployed as part of one-stop-shops for renovations for persons and SMEs with the local public body (i.e. energy agency or building operator) serving as a gateway and advising organisations during renovations. Full transparency provided by the solution would enable third-parties to quickly and easily contribute at any stage of a renovation project.

Suggested Instruments: Launch a topic for RIA or IA of €6-10 million Euros (or a dedicated PCP of €8-10 million) for development and testing. If it is also to be tested as part of a one-stop-shop, the sum should be increased as it may require significant personal effort.

Remarks: Given the market research conducted by the procuRE PCP and the request conducted through the PCP, the market is not expected to deliver the product by itself as the 'cost' of intransparency and inefficiency can be fully externalised to the procuring public organisations (e.g. cities and regions). Public action is advised.

5.4 Encourage the establishment of turn-key providers able to integrate and deploy efficiency, renewable energy and smartness

Background

Active system integration increases the interdependencies and complexity of renovations both regarding physical connections (i.e. wires, piping) and IT-systems during design and implementation. During design, interoperability must be ensured which, however, is often complicated as the leading or most restrictive system might only emerge during planning. Also during implementation, it is helpful if the system is considered as a whole to ensure that all use cases are implemented.

As described above it is often necessary to contract multiple trades during renovations. This complexity results in greater need of communication, mistakes and as a result of both costs.

Finally, renovations with multiple interconnected systems imply friction during operation, clear responsibility for guarantee and maintenance.

As of today, only a small number of turnkey providers able to conduct an active-system renovation exist. Turnkey providers are – at the minimum – contractors able to involve and provide all necessary trades. By extension, they also typically offer design and planning services also offering start to end services.

This paper argues that establishment of turnkey providers, especially in connection with active and smart systems, should be supported.

procuRE insights (complementing background)

During procuRE, suppliers specialised on holistic and systemic renovation had to develop six Renovation Packages for six buildings in direct exchange with the cities. Ultimately, two suppliers were selected and are installing three buildings each.

Despite procurer's direct access to local subcontractors, the selection and coordination of subcontractors required extensive effort. In some cases, local project managers needed to be hired. In any case a local face to the customer and to the sub-contractors is crucial for success.

Recommendation/Request

Support, incentivise and facilitate the creation of turnkey-providers, particularly in the field of smart and renewable energy renovations.

Suggested Instruments: CSAs documenting the need and supporting the creation and merger of businesses to become turnkey providers on local level.

6 procuRE Challenge Brief

This section documents the original technical Challenge Brief. The above analysis is focused on the systemic issues of building stock renovation and lessons learnt. The Challenge Brief goes into further detail of the technical and operational challenges of municipalities to renovate (e.g. complexity, limited resources etc).

Elements of Challenge Brief may be useful to procurers of follow-up innovation or related services.

In particular, procuRE had to develop an indicator set capable of properly assessing renewable production and use performance from a building perspective we consider extremely valuable as the indicators commonly used reflect the grid or production side but not the building as a whole.

6.1 System Integration (T1)

6.1.1 Renovation Approach to achieve 100% RES in existing buildings.

Challenge: According to the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive 2018/844/EU (EPBD), the energy performance of a building shall be determined on the calculated or the **actual annual energy demand** for meeting the different needs associated with its typical use, including the energy demand for heating and cooling to maintain the desired indoor comfort, and for providing domestic hot water. In procuRE, the electricity consumption of all appliances and systems within the building are to be included in the actual final annual energy demand.

The actual annual energy demand of a building is, to the greatest economically feasible extent, to be covered by **on-site renewable energy sources**. “On-site” refers to the building and its nearest vicinity – air, surface, ground and underground –, which, in any case, cannot exceed the building premises or attached structures. Although, for some Demonstration Sites large land surface is available, the procurers want to make sure that the solutions adopted are highly replicable at all their building stock. During the project, solution proposals for functional structures within described perimeters (e.g. courtyard) will be assessed during Co-Design on a case-by-case basis. The extent to which this goal is met is measured with indicators. Energy drawn from networks or otherwise delivered to the site is not an on-site energy resource.

Self-consumption is to be maximised hereby reducing interaction with energy networks. Local and temporal disparities between the production and use of renewable energy in buildings should be considered with sufficient frequency. Energy networks can be relied on to cover exceptional weather, failures etc.

The impact of operators and occupants increases in highly efficient and integrated buildings. The dimensions of **control, comfort and costs** are to be balanced in the overall approach.

6.1.2 System package design

Context: Most current energy retrofit projects do not set out from application of an adequate set of tools, but are disjointed, involving only one or a few buildings, and design starts more or less from scratch in each project. Also, many current retrofit projects result in buildings which do not operate as designed. Specific efficiency measures in the design are either not designed with the users in mind or are often not respected in construction and operation, resulting in performance not matching the original design intent. In some instances, individual systems are optimised impeding the efficiency of

other systems or the building as a whole. In addition, the specification of building performance is often limited to targets for final energy or primary energy use after retrofit. In consequence, Continuous Commissioning is often not possible. Current contractors often externalise the effort of coordinating specialists to procurers who do not have the necessary resources and in-house expertise to perform these tasks efficiently and effectively.

Challenge: Suppliers are expected to offer a fully documented Renovation Approach which represents the full mastery of system specifications, independent of the size, type, and location of the building. Design procedures in the Approach are to minimise the planning efforts, concentrating and organising the necessary expertise from specialists, in particular of complex HVAC systems. The Renovation Approach must include a modular and adaptable set of technologies for energy production, storage, and management with effective and reliable components. Challenges for each of these technologies are described in the following sections.

As part of the Renovation Approach, suppliers must include comprehensive design procedures which can be as easily applied to projects covering single-buildings renovations and scalable to larger portfolio renovations anywhere in Europe. The following elements are considered the minimum necessary:

A clearly specified **design workflow** extending across the entire renovation process (design to operation) and the entire value chain. This must enable all disciplines (architects, engineers, technology providers, system integrator, energy manager...), procurers, building occupants and other stakeholders to exchange information and participate in design with clear trigger points and checks to ensure all required specialists (e.g., HVAC) and stakeholders are involved. Current reliance on procurers to fill these gaps must not be continued. The workflow is also to explain and ensure that all regulation and code requirements are met. For interaction with procurers and in support of their decision-making, the workflow has a specific “Interface to Procurers”.

A **modelling and selection methodology** enabling the supplier to quickly select the best suited components for any given set of buildings, e.g. from the technologies and services mentioned in the Sections 1.1.3 to 1.1.6. This includes any components to complete the HVAC design.

The **output** of these efforts results in a Renovation Package which is specific to one building, containing clear definition of components and systems performance specifications that can easily be understood by non-technical personnel. The Renovation Packages generated must consider current building characteristics, future building use, context, regulatory framework, and climate at the location of the building.

Further elements may be included by suppliers. **Procurers will welcome innovative platforms, such as BIM or others**, capable of linking stakeholders, integrating data streams, highlighting decision requirements, and providing necessary tools for modelling and verification, including to measure the energy, comfort, and health performance, as well as acting or offering building logbooks. It is considered a merit if a platform centralises and harmonises core processes from initial design to operation. This does not preclude attaching value-adding modules or micro-services from one or more third-party vendors.

6.1.3 System package monitoring and management

Context: Most current systems for monitoring and managing buildings in operation still treat each component of a system as a separate unit, with a specific function which is independent of the others.

This impedes attempts at optimal operation of the whole system. This fragmented approach is often reflected in the structure of databases. To optimise behaviour and settings, operators and occupants must analyse multiple components in parallel, themselves. Monitoring and management hardware and software can offer more.

Challenge: Suppliers are challenged to include in their Renovation Approach a streamlined approach to components and processes for the operation phase of the building. Management and monitoring are to provide a “second view” on the building to ensure that design performance is achieved during operation without impeding other performance characteristics (e. g., comfort). The automated and continuous assessment of the monitoring data available needs to be the basis for energy efficiency optimisation and Continuous Commissioning. As occupants are central to the functioning of each building – there is no smart building without informed and smart users – the monitoring systems **must have user interfaces that deliver easy-to-understand information to support behaviour change** (see T3).

Suppliers are expected to define clear and meaningful **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** that allow the building energy performance to be evaluated from an energy and environmental point of view at appliance, system and building levels as well as comfort and other critical or desirable functions. A mandatory set is described in T2. **Minimum and targeted performance** values are to be defined for applicable KPIs, complemented by, and linked to contractual regulations regarding costs and conditions, among other aspects, in case of divergence. These indicators should be defined in a way to demonstrate, through a Continuous Commissioning, the assessed performance also during the building operation, considering the metering and billing of energy use. These indicators give a comprehensive overview of the building, including flexibility, energy efficiency, occupant comfort, awareness and satisfaction, Smart Readiness Indicator.

For an efficient collection of measurements and a reliable calculation of the indicators, a **Monitoring System Guideline** needs to be developed where the minimum set of requirements (sensors and meters) for the monitoring and control system to be installed are defined taking precisions and tolerance fully into account. If additional sensors are deemed to provide added-value or be requested by procurers during Co-Design, these are to be documented in a subsection, including an explanation of their purpose. This Guideline will also contain the definition of all procedures linked to assess the minimum and targeted performance parameters, also feeding into Continuous Commissioning. The system must be able to recognise **manual temporary overrides** by building operators diverging from the automated management and calculate and verifiably record any additional costs resulting from such activity. Cases of divergence are to be collected, summarised, and presented as part of Continuous Commissioning procedure.

In addition to this, the monitoring system should be equipped with a remote facility and an energy management system with control and maintenance features for the building’s technical systems. The **BEMS** (Building Energy Management System) should base the control not only on fixed schedules, but also on occupation, occupant behaviours and needs, system efficiency, RES availability, storage state of charge and network energy utilisation peaks and fares, among other parameters. Forecasts are to cover beyond the near-term future (i.e. next hours). The system should include easy access for building operators to override system settings temporarily, record the reasons for such activity and indicate the consequence of such activity. It should be transparent to the operator when or whether the system restores automated control. The use of **smart controls** based on predictive or advanced rule-based controls would be a plus.

The system shall also create minimal and targeted information for informing and influencing occupant behaviour when deemed necessary. Upon request, it should be possible to integrate easily understandable graphics and core figures in public displays or websites linked to the building.

Similarly, as fault detection and diagnostics reduce energy consumption and discomfort due to interruption of the service, **predictive maintenance strategies** should be offered to guarantee the early detection of malfunctioning components, extend equipment lifespan, the reduction of safety, health, environmental and quality risks, as well as overall reduced costs.

6.1.4 Energy production and distribution components

Context: Public administrations and other building owners are flooded with information on RES and HVAC technologies. However, it is currently very difficult for retrofit procurers to build the necessary analytical vision of what HVAC and RES solutions they should adopt and procure for their building stock.

Challenge: suppliers are expected to improve the framework conditions for procurers to select and adopt renewable production and distribution technologies which have a **low final energy use, high renewable energy harvest** and **minimal life cycle impact** on the environment and the costs (LCA and LCC). Suppliers are encouraged to pre-select technologies as part of their Renovation Approach. **As a set, pre-selected technologies must** cover the procuRE climatic zones, regulatory regimes, and contexts, and be able to be safely applied to offices and schools. Most technologies should be already on the market or soon ready to be commercialised, with adaptation to the social, economic, regulatory, and environmental context of the Buyers Group Demonstration Sites, completed or at least planned.

Suppliers are expected to mostly select **proven technologies** that are cost-effective and easy-to-install, with **performance demonstrated** by standards or specifications or for selected core components, demonstrated during prototype testing in Phase II. A **minimal and coherent set** of scalable and modular pre-selected technologies capable of delivering all above will be considered a plus.

Information provided as part of the Renovation Approach for inclusion in Renovation Packages must **include core descriptions and indicators** enabling procurers to acquire and improve the knowledge base to continuously speed up and improve decisions during Co-Design and with view on multiple future renovations of the building stock using the Renovation Approach.

6.1.5 Energy storage components

Context: Energy storage will play a key role in enabling the EU to develop a low-carbon society and to ensure lasting energy flexibility and security. For a 100% RES driven building, the challenge is to have a balance between supply and demand. For this, the use of thermal and electric storage becomes key for increasing the building flexibility, shifting loads, and shaving peaks.

Challenge: suppliers are expected to improve the framework conditions for procurers to select and adopt thermal and electric storages technologies which **maximise the self-use** of the renewable energy produced on-site, they balance **(high) specific energy storage capacity, low specific investment cost** and **minimal life cycle impact** on the environment and the costs (LCA and LCC) depending on building constraints. Suppliers are encouraged to pre-select technologies as part of

their Renovation Approach. **As a set, pre-selected technologies must** cover procuRE climatic zones, regulatory regimes and contexts and be able to be safely applied to offices and schools. Most technologies should be already on the market or soon ready to be commercialised, with adaptation to the social, economic, regulatory, and environmental context of the Buyers Group Demonstration Sites completed or at least planned.

Suppliers need to describe how they will construct safe and **reliable advanced energy storage solutions** based on **market or ready to be commercialised** individual components, their performance, constraints, and requirements (e.g., system, space). **Proven technologies** should be cost-effective and easy-to-install, with **performance** ensured by specifications or compliance with standards or shown for selected core components or integrated during prototype testing in Phase II. A **minimal and coherent set** of scalable and modular pre-selected technologies capable of delivering all above will be considered a plus.

Information provided as part of the Renovation Approach for inclusion in Renovation Packages must **include core descriptions and indicators**, in particular on **optimal storage choice and scale**, enabling procurers to acquire and improve the knowledge base to continuously speed up and improve decisions during Co-Design and with view on multiple future renovations of the building stock using the Renovation Approach.

6.1.6 Energy management components

Context: Integration of RES, energy storages and efficient components in a comfortable and healthy environment requires active control of the building technical systems, and functional information easily accessible to operators and occupants. Current Facility Management and Building Energy Management Systems (BEMS) do not cover all segments and provide insufficient information to ensure 100% RES operation.

Challenge: Suppliers are encouraged to pre-select technologies as part of their Renovation Approach. **As a set, pre-selected technologies must** cover all relevant use cases, regulatory regimes and contexts and be safely applied to offices and schools and **integrate legacy equipment** and installations. Most technologies should be already on the market or soon ready to be commercialised, with adaptation to the social, economic, regulatory, and environmental context of the Buyers Group Demonstration Sites completed or at least planned. **Proven technologies** should be cost-effective and easy-to-install, with **performance demonstrated** by standards or specifications or for selected core components or integrated during prototype testing in Phase II. A **minimal and coherent set** of scalable and modular pre-selected technologies capable of delivering all below will be considered a plus. (It will be possible to update the list of building level components during the project).

Suppliers are requested to select **cost-effective, low-impact monitoring and control systems**, devoted to gather data from sensors installed at zone and central levels, and to activate and optimise HVAC and electricity management. Solutions will need to be **highly flexible** to adapt to any HVAC system, centralised or local. **New generation**, wireless and self-powered sensors will gather information from storage, from the indoor and external environment and from the HVAC system, critical systems etc. **Actuators** or information and communications technology (ICT) solutions activate relevant legacy devices ensuring they can be monitored and controlled where necessary. All newly installed equipment (production, distribution, storage) shall either support all required functions by default or be equipped with necessary devices. On building level, information and

commands are sent and collected by a **central control unit** capable to communicate with all technical systems using **stable and non-intrusive communication protocols and standards**. **State of the art IT-security strategies** are to be provided for the implemented system. It is not the aim to digitise every single aspect of the building, but digitalisation is a key aspect for achieving 100% RES operation, comfort, and a healthy environment.

A challenge lies in **integrating all data sources and making systems interoperable**. Independent of how (e.g., database formats, AI) and where (e.g., fog, edge, cloud) this is achieved, the following **functionalities** are to be provided to relevant actors in one or several systems **using harmonised and suitable interfaces and visualisations** which are comprehensible for stakeholders with different backgrounds and skills:

- Features of usual Facility Management solutions for procurers and operators
- Features of usual Building Energy Management solutions (BEMS) for procurers and operators
- Use and evaluation of indicators building, system and component performance
- Reports and insights for the Continuous Commissioning and maintenance process
- Documentation and automated entries into a building logbook (ideally linked to or a continuation of the Renovation Packages)
- Export or linking functionality to city-wide energy management solutions and/or BIM platforms
- Meaningful and timely information provided by data analysis algorithms on energy consumption, comfort, and health for occupants (to be utilised as part of T3)

Procurers welcome solutions in which all or some operator user and procurer user facing functionality is centralised in one innovative (BIM) platform. It is considered a plus if the operational processes and interfaces are a continuation of the system package design workflows using the same solutions. An additional plus would be if the building logbook and specific Renovation Packages are strongly linked.

6.2 Degree of achievement of objectives in reference / demonstration buildings (T2)

In addition to demonstrating the innovativeness and solidity of their proposals all along the design and commissioning phases by means of qualitative information provided, the suppliers are requested to assess and provide quantitative indicators showing the energy efficiency, environmental impact, and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) levels achieved through the set of measures proposed during design phases and to be verified after systems commissioning.

6.2.1 Energy Key Performance Indicators

The energy performance KPIs assess how effectively on-site RES will be harvested and exploited. In the calculation of KPIs, one year is defined as 8760 hours.

Final energy consumption (E_F)

This indicator refers to the utilisation of different energy vectors to cover the energy demand of the building independently of their origin, either local or remote (i.e., energy networks). The procurers

want to make sure first that the best technologies with the least overall costs are exploited, minimising the energy needed on site.

The suppliers are requested to assess and provide final energy consumption values for each of the energy vectors (e. g. thermal, electric) utilised on site, at least on an hourly basis for the entire year. For each building accounted for in the specific design phase, the suppliers are requested to provide both whole-building energy consumption expressed in kWh/h and specific energy consumption per gross building volume (including façades volume) expressed in kWh/(m³h). In addition to these values, suppliers are also requested to assess and provide yearly final energy consumption both in MWh/y and kWh/(m³y). The yearly final energy consumption values are obtained integrating the hourly final energy consumption over the entire year.

Assessment: The procurers will use both yearly final energy consumption values (MWh/y and kWh/(m³y)) for the quantitative assessment of the system performance, and the hourly distribution to verify the calculations presented.

Both dynamic simulations and semi-dynamic methods accepted by European and National norms are acceptable calculation methods. The suppliers are requested to provide indication on the calculation method and the boundary conditions adopted, together with the results obtained as part of the offer and future deliverables at the end of each design phase.

On-site renewable energy production (RE_P)

This indicator refers to the on-site production of renewable energy for the different energy vectors utilised on-site. Procurers want to make sure that the best available technologies are exploited, maximising the coverage of the energy needed on site by means of locally available RES.

“On-site” refers to the building and its nearest vicinity – air, surface, ground and underground –, which, in any case, cannot exceed the building premises or attached structures. Although, for some Demonstration Sites large land surface is available, the procurers want to make sure that the solutions adopted are highly replicable at all their building stock. During the project, solution proposals for functional structures within described perimeters (e.g., courtyard) will be assessed during Co-Design on a case-by-case basis.

The suppliers are requested to assess and provide on-site renewable energy production values for each of the energy vectors utilised on site, at least on an hourly basis for the entire year. For each building accounted for in the specific design phase, the suppliers are requested to provide both overall on-site renewable energy production expressed in kWh/h and specific renewable energy production per gross building volume (including façades volume) expressed in kWh/(m³h). In addition to these values, suppliers are also requested to assess and provide yearly on-site renewable energy production both in MWh/y and kWh/(m³y). The yearly on-site renewable energy production values are obtained by integrating the hourly on-site renewable energy production over the entire year.

Assessment: The procurers will use both yearly on-site renewable energy production values (MWh/y and kWh/(m³y)) for the quantitative assessment of the system performance, and the hourly distribution to verify the calculations presented.

Both dynamic simulations and semi-dynamic methods accepted by European norms are acceptable as calculation methods. The suppliers must provide descriptions of the calculation method and the

adopted boundary conditions, together with the results obtained as part of the deliverables at the end of each design phase.

Renewable energy share (RE_Sh)

This indicator states the fraction of final energy consumed that is either covered by renewable energy produced on-site during the same timeframe or previously produced and stored on-site. The suppliers are requested to assess and provide renewable energy share values for each of the energy vectors utilised on site, at least on an hourly basis for the entire year.

This indicator is calculated for each energy vector “j” using the following formula:

$$RE_Sh_{i,j} = \frac{(E_{REU,i} + E_{EFS,i})}{E_{F,i}} \Big|_j$$

Where:

- $RE_Sh_{i,j}$ is the renewable energy share calculated at hour “i”, for each of the energy vectors “j” covered through renewable energy.
- $E_{REU,i}$ is the renewable energy produced on-site at hour “i” and used to cover a final energy use during the same hour.
- $E_{EFS,i}$ is the renewable energy previously generated and stored on-site used to cover the final energy use during hour “i”.
- $E_{F,i}$ is the final energy consumption at hour “i”, for each of the energy vectors “j”.

In addition to hourly values, suppliers are also requested to assess and provide yearly renewable energy share values. For each energy vector “j”, the yearly on-site renewable energy share value is obtained as the integral of the hourly values:

$$RE_PCR_{Y,j} = \frac{\sum_1^{8760} E_{REP,i}}{\sum_1^{8760} E_{F,i}} \Big|_j$$

Assessment: The procurers will use both the yearly renewable energy production to consumption ratio for the quantitative assessment of the system performance, and the hourly values distribution to check whether an attempt has been placed on continuously balancing local renewable energy production and the building’s final energy use. As some buildings like schools are not in use during relevant periods of the day and of the year, a better matching reduces the need for storage capacity installed optimising the utilisation of renewable energy produced on-site.

On-site renewable energy utilisation (RE_UT)

This indicator refers to the renewable energy that is produced and used or stored on site, hence without being exported and then re-imported to the building premises. Export/Import of on-site produced renewable energy has a cost for the community, both environmental and economic, due to losses, infrastructures to be set up, etc. The procurers want to make sure that the burden onto the community is minimised technically and economically as much as possible. The suppliers are requested to assess and provide on-site renewable energy utilisation values for each of the energy vectors utilised on site, at least on an hourly basis. The values should be calculated as the ratio of renewable energy produced and used or stored on-site along the considered timeframe, and the renewable energy produced in the same timeframe. The on-site renewable energy utilisation shall be calculated as:

$$RE_UT_{i,j} = \frac{(E_{REU,i} + E_{ETS,i})}{E_{REP,i}} \Big|_j$$

Where:

- $RE_UT_{i,j}$ is the renewable energy utilisation calculated at hour “i”, for each of the energy vectors “j” covered through renewable energy.
- $E_{REU,i}$ is the renewable energy produced at hour “i” and used to cover a final energy use during the same hour.
- $E_{ETS,i}$ is the renewable energy produced and stored on-site at hour “i”.
- $E_{REP,i}$ is the total renewable energy produced on-site at hour “i”, for each of the energy vectors “j”.

In addition to the hourly values, suppliers are required to assess and provide yearly on-site renewable energy utilisation values. For each energy vector “j”, the yearly on-site renewable energy utilisation value shall be calculated as:

$$RE_UT_{Y,j} = \frac{\sum_1^{8760} (E_{REU,i} + E_{ETS,i})}{\sum_1^{8760} E_{REP,i}} \Big|_j$$

Assessment: The procurers will use both yearly on-site renewable energy utilisation values for the quantitative assessment of the system performance, and the hourly values distribution to check whether continuous balancing of local renewable energy production and utilisation has been achieved.

6.2.2 IEQ Key Performance Indicators

Retrofitting of buildings should not have only an energy dimension, but also consider users, whose health and welfare are of utmost relevance for the Procurers. Accordingly, IEQ should be considered as a key element of the Suppliers’ proposals.

Starting in Phase I, more or less stringent IEQ requirements for each Demonstration Sites might be negotiated with the procurers through the Co-Design procedure. Better comfort conditions offered, e.g., accounting for improved humidity control compared to the minimum normative requirements, will be a merit.

Indoor air temperature (IEQ_T)

Suppliers are requested to respect minimum requirements in terms of thermo-hygrometric air conditions as per European and national normative. During occupancy hours, the temperature should never fall below 21°C nor exceed 25°C.

Assessment: The procurers will use the total number of hours during which the indoor air temperature level is being exceeded for the quantitative assessment of the system performance, and the hourly distribution to check how continuous achieved conditions are.

Indoor air quality (IEQ_AQ)

Suppliers are requested to assure that suitable air quality conditions are delivered to the building users during occupancy hours, according to the best practices and technologies available today and in line with the European and national regulatory requirements.

The suppliers are requested to assess and provide air quality conditions values at least in terms of ppm of CO₂ and provide the number of hours above the threshold of 1000 ppm CO₂. The suppliers are requested to provide descriptions of the calculation method and the adopted boundary conditions, together with the results obtained as part of the deliverables at the end of each design phase.

Assessment: The procurers will use the average CO₂ value and the total number of hours during which CO₂-threshold is being exceeded for the quantitative assessment of the system performance, and the hourly distribution to check how continuous achieved conditions are.

Lighting conditions (IEQ_LC)

Suppliers are requested to assure that comfortable lighting conditions are delivered to the building users during occupancy hours, according to the best practices and technologies available today and the European and national regulatory requirements.

The suppliers are requested to assess and provide illuminance values in lux (cd/m²), UGR (Unified Glare Index) and CRI (Colour Rendering Index) at representative working/training places. Both dynamic simulations and semi-dynamic methods, accounting for coupled artificial and natural lighting effects and for automated controls and accepted by European norms are acceptable calculation methods. The suppliers are requested to provide indication on the calculation method and the boundary conditions adopted, together with the results obtained as part of the deliverables at the end of each design phase.

6.2.3 Environmental Key Performance Indicators

CO₂ emissions during operation (E_CO2)

The performance indicator relates on the carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions of the proposed retrofit solution during building operation; the emissions values are to be computed based on the net final energy drawn from energy networks. For each energy vector imported on site, the suppliers are requested to use CO₂ emission factors derived from the most recent Covenant of Mayors (CoM) Emission Factors⁹. During the proposal, the most recent default values are to be used. During the project, national emission values reported in the CoM resource for each Demonstration Site are to be used.

Assessment: The procurers will use the total from all vectors for the quantitative assessment of the system performance.

6.3 Training & Education of professionals and users (T3)

Context: Operators – including energy professionally employed by the municipality as well as third-party contractors needed for repairs etc. – are faced with increasing complexity of building operation with many contractors having little to no experience with digital solutions. Whilst some issues are structural such as the lack of vocational education and training (VET), the suppliers of solutions also often consider training to be the responsibility of the customers.

⁹ [Joint Research Centre Data Catalogue - CoM Default Emission Factors - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/table.do?tab=table&init=1&language=en&plugin=1)

Occupants' behaviour and habits influence the performance of a building, and more so in highly efficient and automated buildings. There is a significant gap between what is known to work to engage individuals in behaviour change and what is currently being applied in practice in the energy efficiency domain. Projects for public buildings tend to address the collective rather than the individual which leads to the typical problems surrounding the use of public resources and personal involvement.

Challenge: Suppliers are expected to deploy innovative training and education methods and materials. Learning should be **blended in daily use**, in particular for ICT and software. The flow between usage and learning should be seamless, not creating a burden or a substantial effort to increase knowledge.

Training of operators

ICT-systems should be intuitive and instructive with learning incorporated using recent best practice, especially when new features are deployed. Suppliers will describe how assistance is provided transparently across systems and technologies. A single touch point would be considered a plus. Shared viewing solutions and / or secure remote desktops are expected.

Suppliers provide a **learning platform** including a curated (self-)training programme for municipality staff including operators and if helpful procurers. The programme should be adapted to the requirements of the specific building based on the Renovation Package and be responsive to pre-existing user knowledge. Procurers have no preference as to the formats used as part of the programme.

Documentation of systems and hardware should clearly describe responsibilities in operation, regarding automation and any manual tasks needed on-site. Suppliers are expected to provide easily understandable materials and / or demonstrate innovative and interactive materials, (e.g. embedding existing smartphones and tablets for augmented realities) accessible for all professional levels including installers. In Phase III, instructions are to be provided in the official languages, and other native languages spoken by installers, where applicable.

Regarding **third-party contractors**, suppliers are to outline what knowledge will be required for reliable and timely operation and maintenance activities and how this is ensured. Solutions could include training and accrediting installers.

If full-service providers are to minimise dependency on inexperienced third-party installers in the long-term reducing the need for above, this should be referenced here, and quality and feasibility of the approach clearly described as part of PM2/3.

Education of occupants

The supplier's approach to education will ensure the technical solution described above is feasible with users and will help to avoid the traditional operator-occupant conflict regarding comfort and requested, actual and perceived control.

Suppliers are expected to develop a **solution that makes occupants aware of their behaviour's impact** and, in combination with carefully tailored training measures, makes them feel responsible to reflect on their behaviour if it is energetically relevant or if health could be improved without increasing consumption. Suppliers will offer information and feedback to occupants which suggests specific action including information on how the building's consumption levels would change as well as the impact (e.g. climate impact, monetary terms) of not acting documented to be most successful

in the given context. The entire system will be designed to ensure that all the building occupants (workers, teacher, pupils...) can easily understand and interact with the building without any need for extensive training.

Children and other curious occupants are to be considered with creative features. Both, on-the-spot learning elements for energy usage/savings, data or technology used in the building (e.g., via QR-Codes, printable information) as well as serious games or gamification features (e.g. treasure hunts, orienteering, simulations) are to be provided. Games are accessible to teachers and can be used during on an average school hour and, where possible without additional effort, incorporate live data. Long-term competitions such as leading boards or topical challenges are only to be introduced if they are clearly incorporated into the overall education approach.

Suppliers are invited to, where possible, utilise and reference personas described in **Error! Reference source not found.** in their descriptions of services.

Investment and energy service contracting and financing models / Costs (CF1)

Context: Multiple barriers for public administrations exist to progress as expected in the Renovation Wave and to achieve 2050 targets. The most obvious are design and investments costs which limit the number of renovations which can be financed per year. Although the market is offering novel contracts to large private projects, these concepts remain often inaccessible for public procurers aiming to retrofit individual buildings (unattractive investment) and / or aiming for holistic and complex solutions as envisaged (perception of risk) and /or inadequate information performance on the energy efficiency measures is provided (both). As presented in the technical section, many procurers may not have the capacity or organisational capability to act on this gap.

Since the issues arise from a lack of structured information, the Renovation Approach is to provide more clarity on the overall framework conditions to be deployed and in a second step calculate total cost of ownership for individual Renovation Packages, digressing from the current practice and preference of most procurers.

Challenge: Suppliers are expected to develop and deliver an **innovative approach to the financing of energy renovation** and following O&M including (i) technical and financial due diligence (ii) financial risk quantification; (iii) identification of eligible public funding; (iv) access to platforms enabling matching of investment demand and offers.

Leveraging available funding opportunities (public and/or private), suppliers must describe a **financing scheme for single building retrofits and** are expected to also offer a separate or complementary **portfolio level scheme**. These schemes leverage investment capital for public procurers able to cluster building retrofit actions to increase the scale of investment to make it more attractive to investors and reduce risk.

Independent of the volume of the retrofit, the approach should clearly describe and quantify the investment (capex), energy services (opex) and contracting models as well as their costs and conditions to be used at least in the countries represented by the Buyers Group. **Procurers do not state a requirement or specific preference for any contracting model.**

The approach should achieve the following to the largest extent possible:

- **Enable a larger number of renovations per year** by flattening or reducing the cost curve
- Increase **confidence on benefits and reduce connected risks** for procurers and investors by creating transparency about all aspects of models/funding and existing experience with it
- Integrate **innovative financing methods** with funding opportunities to leverage a wider range of funds, including existing and upcoming (inter)national funding schemes for specific Renovation Packages
- Produce swiftly preliminary and detailed **economic plans** including
 - structure of contracts for energy and facility management services,
 - clarity on ownerships and a clear and concise calculation of all costs for procurers at least on yearly basis (e.g. annual fees, design, investment, operation, and maintenance costs), including:
 - the use of incentives,
 - contracting schemes and
 - financing models
 - as well as uncomplicated rule set for discretions from performance benchmark / KPIs induced by either party
- Where relevant consider the EU taxonomy for sustainable activities.

It would be considered a plus if future contracts would actively promote the social dimension of any action, creating new business opportunities and generating highly skilled jobs at local level as part of the planning, installing, and managing of the renovation solutions they will deliver.

6.4 Interface to procurers (PM1)

Context: Currently, operators of building cannot procure a full Renovation Package or the necessary service from one provider and are therefore forced to buy-in and sometimes coordinate services and works increasing the number of possible points of failure. This situation is overburdening the customer in terms of resources and the expertise required to be kept in-house.

Challenge: suppliers are expected to remove procurers from the inner workflow of system package design to the largest extent possible whilst enabling procurers whenever required to make rapid and informed decisions on the elements of the Renovation Package as presented. The challenge lies in finding the best balance between information and involvement. Ideally, the same interface is also during operation.

6.4.1 Toolkit

A solution is required to manage information collection and exchange, file access and documentation with procurers (and possibly all specialists or other external stakeholders). It provides access to a recent version of the Renovation Package as well as the history. The solution must require as little training as possible. The solution could be integrated into a BIM solution or utilise existing cloud-based solutions. The solution must observe necessary certifications and data safety and protection regulation.

Suppliers are free in suggesting how, where and when information is exchanged, or decisions are triggered. These procedures are to be described for design, planning and implementation (Co-Design Procedure) as well as operation & maintenance (Continuous Commissioning) clearly linking the description to the related supplier workflows.

Lesson: This should be strictly defined by procurers. Suppliers and IT providers are not able to anticipate procurer's needs and consider the process as a whole. Strictly define what is required or even better provide infrastructure.

The partners of procuRE are working on other efforts to gain this dramatic effectiveness and efficiency advantage in the Urban Innovation project ZEROit in the German market and are considering an effort which is more broadly applicable.

6.4.2 Co-Design Procedure

The initial commissioning of a renovation is complex and might require input or decisions from procurers at various points in time. Depending on the scope of the renovation, a wide range of requirements need to be collected from varying roles at the procuring organisation (individuals with decision making power or controlling the budget), operators of the building (energy or facility managers) and occupants to the extent possible. Additionally, these inputs need to be aligned with a wide range of regulations and building codes (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

An efficient, effective, and reliable Co-Design Procedure includes at least the following:

- One-face to the customer approach
- Clarity on responsibilities and timing
- A process for information requests from supplier to procurer ensuring minimal friction and effort
- Regular exchange meetings in which suppliers inform the procurers about the most recent version of the Renovation Package and state of work
- Decision making tools based on relevant information and the documentation in Renovation Packages
- Transparency on the most recent version and recent changes in the Renovation Package aiding quick orientation by procurers

Suppliers should take the following key principles into consideration:

- It is inclusive as it **includes representatives from all stakeholder groups involved** in the future service delivery and utilises feedback, advice and decisions service from procurers, operators, possibly occupants and other professionals in the field,
- It is **actor-centred** as each step consists of the actions of individual or collective entities (persons or organisations) and is described, enacted, and analysed in that perspective,
- It is **iterative** in its overall approach and in each step, as changes and adaptations are a natural part of the process,
- It is **evaluative** since each step, its alignment with the previous ones (summative perspective) and its anticipated impacts on following steps (formative perspective) are evaluated empirically,
- It is **outcome-focused** as it is designed to achieve outcomes, where the potential solutions can be rapidly tested, effectiveness measured, and the scaling of these solutions can be developed with stakeholders and in context.

6.4.3 Continuous Commissioning

Continuous Commissioning should be a highly standardised process requiring little effort on the procurer side. Among others, clear timelines, trigger points for actions, report formats, meeting agendas ensure that targeted performance and costs are achieved and any mitigation measures necessary do not lead to sudden cost hikes. Any preparation of a Continuous Commissioning process considers at least:

- Performance against KPIs
- Divergence from performance targets including reasons and costs incurred from operator activity
- Operating and maintenance costs
- Impact of occupant behaviour, unused potentials, and the utilisation of education
- Predictive maintenance
- Recommendations for mitigation and / or optimisation measures

Furthermore, the process should include transparent and open **lessons to be learnt for future renovation measures** in all or specific building types / scenarios to continuously improve the Renovation Approach and as a result future Renovation Packages, anticipating the close relationship supplier and procurer would have when more renovations are triggered.

Wherever possible, Continuous Commissioning should be an extension of the Co-Design Procedure with clear documentation in monitoring and management systems and/ or the logbook.